

A Case Study of Senso Neural Hearing Loss Healed Successfully Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPY) Healing Protocols

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: When some damage to the inner ear occurs, it results in senso neural hearing loss (SNHL). Common causes include exposure to loud noises, genetic factors, or the natural aging process. Medical recommendations generally include hearing aids or assistive devices. This paper presents a case of SNHL treated successfully using Yoga Prana Vidya Healing techniques helping the patient to fully regain normal hearing capabilities.

Method: This paper uses case study method of investigation by going through patient's medical records, YPV healer's records and patient's feedback.

Results: After two days of healing sessions, the patient experienced bearable noise level, By the end of 9 sessions, noise almost reduced and hearing was improved by 80%, and PTA test score reduced from 41 to 28. She attended and learnt Healer development programme Level 1 (HDP L1) course, and she continued with self-healing. A follow up after a year and half showed perfectly normal hearing with PTA score of 13.

Conclusions: Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing protocols have cured the Senso hearing loss in this case, and further research is recommended with appropriate sample size and methodology. In view of being an integrated and holistic system, it will be helpful for the frontline health workers such as doctors and nurses to learn and practice YPV healing protocols to complement their specialties.

KEYWORDS: Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®, Bioplasmic energy healing, Sensoneural hearing loss (SHL), Alternative medicine,

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INTRODUCTION

Senso neural hearing loss

Sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) is the most common type of hearing loss and accounts for the majority of all cases of hearing loss. SNHL refers to any cause of hearing loss due to a pathology of the cochlea, auditory nerve, or central nervous system. Patients with new-onset hearing loss should be investigated and undergo full audiometric evaluation by a multidisciplinary team, including an otolaryngologist, audiologist, radiologist, and speech/language therapist [1]. Many patients with hearing loss find it very isolating, and activities they previously enjoyed, such as going to the cinema, eating at a restaurant, or meeting family and friends, become discouragingly stressful for them, and they often prefer to withdraw from socialising.

SNHL is caused by damage to the structures in inner ear or auditory nerve, and considered to be more than 90 percent of hearing loss cases in adults. Common causes of SNHL include exposure to loud noises, genetic factors, or the natural aging process [2]. A spiralling organ inside inner ear called cochlea contains tiny hairs known as stereocilia. These hairs convert vibrations from sound waves into neural signals that the auditory nerve carries to our brain. Exposure to sounds louder than 85 decibels can damage these hairs. SNHL can range from mild hearing loss (26 to 40 dB) to moderate hearing loss (41-55 dB) to severe (or complete) hearing loss (>71db) depending on the degree of damage. SNHL is not a life-threatening condition, but it is a disability that can interfere with one's ability to communicate if not properly managed [2]. SNHL can occur in one ear or both ears

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depending on the cause. If it onsets gradually, the symptoms might not be obvious without a hearing test. If it is experienced suddenly, the symptoms will appear within several days. People generally notice sudden SNHL upon waking.

Sensorineural hearing loss can lead to:

- trouble hearing sounds when there's background noise
- particular difficulty understanding children's and female voices
- dizziness or balance problems
- trouble hearing high-pitched sounds
- sounds and voices seem muffled
- feeling like you can hear voices but can't understand them
- tinnitus (ringing in your ears)

A complete audiometric evaluation is the best practice standard for evaluating a someone with sensorineural hearing loss. In clinical practice, tuning fork tests, a quick and easy bedside investigation, are usually performed first alongside a pure tone audiogram (PTA) and tympanometry.

There is no cure for age-related hearing loss. If diagnosed with this condition, doctors may recommend:

- hearing aids to help hear better
- assistive devices, such as telephone amplifiers
- lessons in sign language or lip reading (for severe hearing loss)

In some cases, doctors may recommend a cochlear implant, a small electronic device that's surgically implanted into your ear. Cochlear implants can make sounds somewhat louder, but they don't restore normal hearing. This option is only used for people who are severely hard of hearing [2].

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System

Yoga Prana Vidya system (YPV) is based on ancient science which recognises existence of an energy body surrounding the physical body of human beings and generally in all living entities. YPV treats and heals both physical body and energy body, known as bio-plasmic energy body or Aura, which surrounds the physical body. Figures 1 & 2 depict typical energy bodies of a healthy person and sick person respectively.

Figure 1. Energy body of a healthy person

Figure 2. Energy body of a sick person

YPV system does not use any drugs nor any touch. The healer acts as a channel to draw in and transmit Pranic energy by projecting it to the patient's physical body parts as well as to

the respective Chakrams of the energy body which distribute the given energy to the physical body.

Figure 3. Chakram of the energy body

Figure 4. Healer projecting Pranic energy to patient

The chakrams healed in YPV practice are shown in Figure 3 and the process of healer channelizing and projecting Pranic energy (bio-plasmic energy) to the patient is as shown in Figure 4. Proximal healing happens when the patient and healer are in the same room facing each other. Distal healing is when the healer is not in front or even situated far away from the patient, hundreds or even thousands of Kilometers away. Their energy bodies are within the energy body of earth and energy transference from healer to patient happens almost instantly. Radin et al. [3] investigated scientific evidence of distance healing intention therapies and found that significant experimental effects have been observed.

There are 11 major chakrams on our energy body, which control and vitalize all the organs and glands in our body. Chakrams not only control the physical but also psychological aspects of our body. Aura is bioplasmic energy field around our body. Bio means life and plasma is the fourth state of matter. It is hard to see this bio-plasmic energy body with naked eyes, but through GDV photography, the energy field can be captured and visualized. Prana or 'ki' is that life energy that keeps the body alive and healthy.

As integrated system, YPV applies three categories of protocols, these are: (1) Physical and Rhythmic breathing exercises, Forgiveness Sadhana for patient self-practice either by oneself or in groups, (2) Guided Meditations for practice of patients by oneself or in groups including joining the Group Healing sessions online, and (3) Energy healing, either self-healing, or by external trained healer. This way, a

person's physical, mental, and emotional domains are simultaneously healed enabling holistic treatment of co-existing conditions.

A search of relevant literature shows that there are over 60 published research articles on successful applications of YPV protocols in treating a variety of illness conditions as complementary as well as alternative medicine. Some examples of successfully healed cases are - female infertility, Rheumatoid arthritis, various types of addictions, breast cancer, COVID 19, kidney disease, brain stroke, knee-cap dislocation, Hodgkin Lymphoma, Nephrotic syndrome, serious snake bite, hypothyroidism, emergency and first aid, high cholesterol, eye diseases, arterial heart block, diabetes management and difficult medical cases [4-19]. This paper presents a case of Sensoneural hearing loss healed successfully using YPV protocols as alternative medicine.

METHODS

Case study method is used in this paper, by collecting data from patient medical record, YPV healer's record and patient feedback.

CASE REPORT

Patient information and illness

The Patient was a working professional, aged 53, a YPV healer herself and living with her family. She experienced discomfort in the right ear with disturbing noise and was not able to hear properly, since a few days. She consulted an ENT

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specialist, who suggested an audiometry test. The report, dt 12/11/2020 (Annexure 1), showed PTA (Pure Tone Audiometry) score of 41, diagnosed as moderate senso neural hearing loss, and considered functionally impaired. She approached her YPV trainer for healings to treat this illness.

YPV Intervention

She reached out to her YPV trainer for the healings. 9 sessions of healings were done from 12/11/20 to 18/11/20.

The following YPV healing Protocols were applied by the healer.

- Psychotherapy
- Blood cleansing technique
- Internal organ cleansing technique
- For the affected right ear, blue energy tube inserted, cleansed with green, orange, red and energised with gold, greenish violet, greenish yellow and gold for regeneration of ear.
- Ear, jaw, temple, forehead and back head chakras cleansed and further energized with green and gold for regeneration.
- Sublimation of sex chakra energy upto throat and swept to right ear for regeneration.
- Basic, navel and sex chakras energized with red after cleansing.

RESULTS

Within a couple of sessions in first two days, the noise reduced to bearable extent. By the end of total 9 sessions, noise almost reduced and hearing was improved by 80%, and test result on 18/11/2020, showed PTA score of 28 (Annexure 2). She attended Healer development programme Level 1(HDP Level 1) course, in which the healing protocols were taught. She continued with self-healing, as she was a level 3 healer, herself.

FOLLOW UP

On a follow up with the patient in May 2022, she informed the healer that she was having pain and disturbance in the ear. Upon sensing the chakras and related organs by hand scanning, it was found that there was some disturbing energy congestion in the ears and lot of congestion in the brain. Upon enquiry the patient stated that she was in a state of high stress as she was preparing for a new professional certification in her job and she had to handle the new project with new technology which was very challenging for her. Then the healer conducted further 4 healing sessions in a span of 1 week, from 24th May to 30th May 2022 her condition normalised. She further continued her self healings. After that, a PTA test was taken on 20th June 22 which showed a normal score of 13 (Annexure 3).

She feared earlier that her life had come to a standstill because senso neural hearing loss was considered a permanent loss and using hearing aid was the only known solution at that time. However, now the patient felt extremely happy with the improvement gained through YPV healing

DISCUSSION

This case study supports an earlier finding by Mahajan et al (2022) who reported a case of hearing loss due to infection treated by using Yoga Prana vidya (YPV) healing protocols [24]. Literature shows another successful case of Exostosis of ear of an elderly female that was cured using YPV protocols [25]. YPV protocols and techniques have thus been found to be effective in restoring hearing ability without need of any surgery or hearing aids or external devices. Age-related hearing loss is a progressive condition which can get worse over time. That means, timely healing using YPV protocols can help regaining senso neural hearing loss, and one can avoid use of hearing aids or any other form of external devices to improve quality of life.

CONCLUSIONS

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing protocols have cured many types of diseases and health conditions successfully as is evident from a vast number of cases reported including this case of Senso neural hearing loss. Further research is recommended with appropriate sample size and methodology. In view of being an integrated and holistic system, it will be helpful for the frontline health workers such as doctors and nurses to learn and practice YPV healing protocols to complement their specialties.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest

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ANNEXURE

Annexure 1

Annexure 2

A Case Study of Senso Neural Hearing Loss Healed Successfully Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPY) Healing Protocols

Annexure 3

Amplifon India Pvt Ltd		amplifon	
49, Murudeshwara arcade, 27th Main, Jayanagar 9 blk			
Patient Name	[REDACTED]	Date of birth	10-01-1969
Test date:		20-06-2022	

Report comments:
(in dB HL) PTA SRT SIS UCL
Right Ear 13
Left Ear 13

Diagnosis:
Right Ear: Normal Hearing Sensitivity [except at high frequencies]
Left Ear: Normal Hearing Sensitivity

Recommendations:
ENT Review
Counseling & Follow up

Bharath Bhushan K.R. (RCI Reg No: A26615), Senior Audiologist

Name: [REDACTED]
Audiologist: [REDACTED]
20-06-2022

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